

DIRECTORY OF OPEN ACCESS JOURNALS

Annual Highlights 2025

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OUR MISSION

To increase the visibility, accessibility, reputation, usage and impact of quality, peer-reviewed, open access scholarly research journals globally, *regardless of discipline, geography or language.*

THE YEAR IN REVIEW

I'm pleased and proud to share these highlights from 2025, a year of organic growth and progress to secure DOAJ's future and strengthen our core mission of supporting open access journals.

We were delighted to [launch the DOAJ Fonden](#), earlier in the year. This step established DOAJ as a community-led non-profit foundation in Denmark, enhancing our stability, simplifying our administration and ensuring we are accountable to the community. We also marked this new stage in our development by recommitting to the [Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure](#).

The DOAJ index continues to expand, and in January alone, we received over 1000 applications from journals. Alongside our technical infrastructure, we continue to invest the majority of our income in our editorial team, which evaluates journals against our criteria, investigates questionable practices, and curates our journal metadata. In 2025, we expanded the team to support new languages and regions: Germany, Indonesia, Portuguese (Brazil and Portugal). In addition, we completed the first stage of our multi-year editorial workflow project, which will improve efficiency and provide a smoother experience for journals seeking inclusion.

Our community looks to DOAJ's criteria as an indicator of trust, and to our leadership in developing new standards as scholarly publishing evolves. This year, we've formalised [quarterly updates to our criteria](#) to cover emerging business models, specific journal types and AI.

DOAJ is just one of several important infrastructures supporting open access journals, and collaboration between infrastructures enables us to reach more journals and have a greater impact on improving publication standards. We're particularly proud of our [renewed partnership with Latindex](#) on journal quality standards and a [new collaboration with the China National Publications Import and Export Group](#) to support the growing number of Chinese open-access journals with DOAJ indexing. We are also excited to participate in the new European Diamond Capacity Hub, contributing our skills and expertise to support the discoverability and quality assurance of diamond journals across Europe.

Finally, I want to express my gratitude. DOAJ is a community project: a small, dedicated core team boosted by the commitment of over 100 volunteer editors and ambassadors worldwide. This collective effort enables us to achieve an impact well beyond our size, a contribution we were proud to share across more than 150 global events this year. Our work is dependent on you, our global community. We are grateful to all the libraries, publishers, funders and metadata users whose financial support powers our activities. We are delighted to see an increasing number of libraries and organisations prioritising support for the open infrastructures upon which they depend.

JOANNA BALL

Managing Director

DOAJ IN NUMBERS 2025

by 31st December 2025, we had...

22,485

journals indexed

140

countries represented

91

languages represented

Overall in 2025*...

8,887

applications received

2,341

journals accepted

6,427

journals rejected

26%

acceptance rate

BY THE COMMUNITY FOR THE COMMUNITY

Beyond our core team of 26 individuals, DOAJ extends through our global community. Throughout 2025, 90 volunteers from 38 different countries helped us review local-language applications, maintaining the high standards that are expected from us. Alongside them, 667 libraries from 27 countries contributed to our sustainability in 2025.

73%

of our funds come from our community

27%

of our funds come from publishers and aggregators

In 2025, we made agreements with three new consortia, and welcomed 70 new libraries as supporters.

DOAJ operates at the heart of a global network, collaborating with and serving librarians, researchers, publishers, organisations, aggregators and students alike. We extend our deepest gratitude to those who advocate for our mission. Furthermore, we are immensely grateful to our financial supporters; their investment sustains the open infrastructure that maintains trust in scholarly communities worldwide.

UPDATE FROM EDITORIAL

KEY UPDATES FROM EDITORIAL IN 2025

- We initiated quarterly updates to our Guide to Applying.
- We retired the DOAJ Seal
- We launched a label for S2O (Subscribe to Open) journals

MATT HODGKINSON
Head of Editorial

“Five new members joined the editorial team, including myself, growing the team 30% to meet the increasing volume of applications and updates. We moved to quarterly updates to the Guide to Applying; changes include how we handle appeals, our S2O policy, our licensing & copyright page, adding Integrity & Ethics and case reports journals criteria, and best practices for AI.”

As well as assessing new applications, we received 3,568 update requests and completed the re-assessment of indexed journals that were last updated in 2017. We added new fields to our metadata: Last Reviewed date; Subscribe to Open; Mirror journals; Open Journals Collective. To keep pace with the increasing applications and ethical concerns, and changes in our criteria we began the Editorial Workflow Project to revise our internal systems to help with structured assessment of journals. We completed the first stage, with a roadmap for releases over time.

INTEGRITY AND ETHICS

Our Integrity and Ethics team carried out over 400 in-depth investigations into suspicious journals and publishers. 71% of these investigations led to embargoes from the index of at least one year.

CENYU SHEN

Deputy Head of Editorial (Integrity and Ethics)

“This year reflects a shift in our team toward a stronger focus on quality over volume. We dedicated more time to each case due to increasing complexity and our efforts to strengthen review rigour. We have continued to adapt our criteria to address emerging ethical challenges, such as paper mill activities, while further optimising processes to ensure the efficient assessment of problematic journals and publishers.”

EVENTS AND OUTREACH

In 2025, DOAJ team members and Ambassadors attended and presented at more than 150 online and in-person events across 47 countries.

THE IMPORTANCE AND IMPACT OF OUTREACH

As a community-led organisation that both represents and serves users from all over the world, it is important for us to meet and connect with our local and global communities. Our outreach includes sharing our expertise to wider communities and organising training and workshops for local communities, especially from academic communities that are underrepresented in the index.

Increasing the coverage of African journals in DOAJ has been a strategic priority since 2022. As part of this focus, DOAJ has coordinated targeted workshops in several African countries to support journals in understanding and meeting DOAJ's standards.

In 2025, the number of African journals indexed in DOAJ increased by 196, reaching a total of 784. This growth reflects our sustained outreach and capacity-building efforts in the region, led by DOAJ Ambassadors and team members working closely with local journal communities

2025 FOCUS - DIAMOND OA

DIAMOND OPEN ACCESS

At DOAJ, we champion all open access journals, regardless of business model, but we know that our work has the most impact on smaller, community-led journals, most of which don't charge APCs. In 2025, we chose to shine a spotlight on the many aspects of our work that make a difference to community-led journals. Alongside our core indexing, we have strengthened our support for Diamond Open Access through targeted outreach, metadata improvements, and closer collaboration with infrastructure providers and global initiatives. We have also contributed to increasing the visibility of Diamond OA journals, supporting best practices, and engaging with projects that enhance sustainability, interoperability, and regional inclusivity. Together, these efforts reinforce DOAJ's role in enabling a more equitable and community-driven scholarly publishing ecosystem.

DIAMOND OA PROJECTS

The transition from **CRAFT-OA** to the **European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH)** represents a shift from a time-limited project to a permanent, coordinated European infrastructure designed to sustain, align, and scale support for Diamond Open Access publishing through shared services, standards, and community-driven collaboration. It is important for DOAJ because it promotes quality alignment, improves transparency and discoverability of Diamond OA journals, and helps create reliable, standardised benchmarks that strengthen trust and inclusion in the DOAJ.

ALMASI is advancing collaboration between African, Latin American, and European Diamond OA stakeholders, with early achievements including mapping the Diamond OA landscape, fostering partnerships, and identifying priorities for capacity building. The project is already helping to amplify regional expertise and promote more inclusive, globally connected approaches to open access publishing.

DOAJ AND DIAMOND OA 2025

13,831

journals without fees

62%

journals indexed have no fees

CLARA ARMENGOU

Programme Manager

“Working on CRAFT-OA, ALMASI, and now the EDCH has highlighted the importance of supporting diverse, community-led publishing models. Diamond Open Access is not only viable, it's vital for ensuring that knowledge remains accessible and inclusive worldwide.”

PROJECTS AND PARTNERSHIPS

HIGHLIGHTED PROJECTS AND PARTNERSHIPS

We have worked on several projects in 2025, both internal and external:

Research4Life and ASSAf (Academy of Science of South Africa)

Since 2023, our ongoing collaboration with Research4Life and ASSAf has focused on training to prepare journals from Research4Life eligible countries prepare to apply to DOAJ. Building on the success of previous sessions held in English, Spanish, French, and Ukrainian, 2025 marked a significant expansion of our reach. We conducted workshops in Portuguese and piloted a Google Classroom course, which saw an enrollment of over 500 participants.

Latindex

In 2025, we initiated a project with Latindex to index Ibero-American journals in DOAJ. Through this collaboration, we mapped journals not yet in both databases and conducted workshops on the DOAJ application process for South American journals indexed in Latindex. The partners exchanged information and methodologies for identifying journals with questionable practices and we participated in academic events in Argentina, Brazil, Mexico and Peru.

Mir@bel2022

The Mir@bel2022 project (2022–2025) involved 14 partners to support the inclusion of French journals in DOAJ. Key outcomes include French translations of DOAJ resources (including the Guide to Applying with Érudit) and French webinars on DOAJ criteria and the application process. The collaboration also strengthened engagement with the Francophone scholarly publishing community

CNPIEC

In partnership with CNPIEC, we launched the China Open Access Journal Pre-evaluation Working Group in September 2025. From November 2025, this group has been providing a free service to help local journals assess their readiness for DOAJ inclusion. Using a custom evaluation form and website, dedicated staff review submissions and provide feedback to improve journal standards and increase the success rate of official applications.

JASPER

JASPER has now worked with 76 journals either directing them to PKP, or helping to get their content preserved in Internet Archive and CLOCKSS. In May 2025, a journal preserved in CLOCKSS via JASPER was forced to close and the content was triggered - a success story for JASPER

Open Access Journals Toolkit

The OA Journals Toolkit has a full content revision and update of all HTML English sections in 2025, including two new sections on Accessibility and Long-Term Digital Preservation. There were three new languages : Arabic (revised and updated), Portuguese and Spanish. In addition, two new board members were welcomed, read the full update on our blog.

AMBASSADORS

A RENEWED AMBASSADOR PROGRAMME

2025 has been a pilot year for our renewed Ambassador programme. We have implemented new processes, a new structure, recruited new Ambassadors and invested in travel and outreach activities to support our Ambassadors in connecting with their local communities.

2025 DOAJ AMBASSADORS

In 2025, we were delighted to welcome three new members to our global network: Carolina Dias (Brazil), Angela Aikins (West Africa), and Oluchi Okere (West Africa). These additions brought our total presence to 16 Ambassadors representing 13 Low- and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs).

Throughout the year, our team of Ambassadors were incredibly active, leading or participating in 98 workshops and events. They are also engaged with their local communities in other ways, for example through networking, meetings and projects.

We want to thank all of our 2025 DOAJ Ambassadors for their work with local communities to increase awareness and good practice around open access publishing.

Thank

you

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